

CONTRIBUTORY PENSION SCHEME AND EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION TO RETIRE AMONG WORKERS IN AKWA IBOM STATE CIVIL SERVICE

DR. IMOWO UDOMA UDOBIA

Department of Sociology, Ritman University, Ikot Ekpene.

Email: imowoudobia@gmail.com

Phone: +2348023155437

DR NATHANIEL UDOH

Department of Industrial Relations and Personnel Management, Ritman
University, Ikot Ekpene

Email: nathanieludoh99@gmail.com@gmail.com

Phone: +2347082439614

&

DR. GODWIN EDET ESSOH

Department of Industrial Relation and Personnel Management, Ritman
University, Ikot Ekpene.

Abstract

Contributory pension scheme and employee motivation to retire among workers in Akwa Ibom state civil service was conceived on the basis of determining the relationship between contributory pension scheme and motivation to retire among workers in the civil service of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Following the analyses of the work, it was found that a significant relationship exists between ease of access to pension benefits and motivation to retire. This was confirmed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis. The findings of the study reveals that fund administrators' commitment to pension scheme significantly affect motivation to retire in civil service. Following the analyses of the work, it was affirmed that the arguments in the body of the work that contributory pension scheme correlates with motivation to retire in Akwa Ibom State civil service. However, it was recommended that fund administrators should maintain their high level of commitment to management of the pension scheme since no reasonable employee will hesitate to retire when they are due,

Keywords: Employee Motivation, Pension Scheme, Civil Service, Motivation to Retire.

1. INTRODUCTION

Retirement planning in Akwa Ibom State civil service is fraught with many challenges. This affects the motivation to retire negatively. For Nigerian civil servants specially challenged by low levels of income and savings and vast family and social obligations, retirement can be a source of frustration. Some of the social issues that negatively affect workers' motivation to retire in Nigeria include family

size, extended family demands and poor accessibility to health care. Other issues that affect motivation to retire negatively include work role detachment, reduced self-esteem, and loss of social network of professional colleagues. Also, the absence of a social security system to provide for the aged, the young, unemployed and the physically challenge put additional burden on workers' resources (IBTC Pension Managers, 2008).

Bisong (2011) stressed that Akwa Ibom State civil service appeared not to have sufficiently addressed the issue of energizing the workers to positively embrace retirement. Retirement has become a permanent nightmare. Jonathan (2009) observed that retirees' plight in Akwa Ibom civil service is worsened by the fact that they are owed several months pension arrears with no hope for immediate payment. Fear and anxiety has thus become a constant companion of the civil servants in the state preparing for retirement. Failure to properly motivate civil servants to retire may be responsible for a lot of socio economic and psychological problems that affect not only themselves but the society in general.

Elaborating further, Agulanni (2003) observed that as a means of motivating workers towards retirement the government provides income. Work organizations have also adopted the strategy of counseling workers awaiting retirement so that they can look towards post-retirement life positively.

Pension is money paid to a worker after leaving employment. It allows public servants that have worked for 35 years or 60/65 years of age for public servants and professor respectively to receive a maximum pension and gratuity for their different grades and ranks. The pension ordinance of 1951 established in Nigeria took effect from January, 1946. The next was the civil service pension scheme that came into force following the Local Government Pension Scheme of 1977. The first formal pension scheme in Nigeria known as National Provident Fund (NPF) was established in 1961 to cater for the non-pensionable private sector workers. The 2005 Act operates an unfunded Scheme whereas the payment of retirement benefits was based on budgetary provisions (Okechukwu & Ugwu, 2011).

Despite these pension policies, retirement counseling, and the often-organized capacity building, pre-retirement workshops for civil servants in Akwa Ibom State retirees are still exposed to a life of frustration, untold hardship and penury. Failure to have access to pension and gratuity by retirees from federal, state and local governments have aggravated their socio economic and psychological conditions. Retirees are still left to suffer unnecessarily or die in the course of waiting for their benefits.

In Akwa Ibom State, the administration of pension and gratuity is problematic. The fund administrators are not committed to pension obligation. The administration of pension fund does not guarantee financial security to the civil servants. Pension fund administration has become a thorny issue with millions of retired civil servants not

well taken care of after retirement. Many retired workers go through difficulties before they receive their pensions and gratuity.

Bassey (2011) asserted that non-involvement of civil servants in pension management plan has affected their motivation to retire in a significant dimension. Participation in pension management among civil servants in Akwa Ibom State does not follow a team approach that involves workers to foster legitimacy and acceptance. This lack of involvement has not enhanced civil servants' confidence and protection that they are secured as they go into retirement. Additionally, the civil servants are not encouraged by pension funds custodians to save funds for investment. Workers in the state perceive this as depriving them of additional comfort at old age and are thus not motivated towards contented retirement life. Moreover, Bassey (2011), further stressed that retirees often experience high level of disappointment because of lack of easy access to pension benefits. The thought of delay in benefits could result to embarrassing circumstances in post-retirement period such as inability to meet financial obligation, satisfactory health needs etc. Thus, lack of ease of access to pension benefits could be a source of demotivation to civil servants towards a comfortable retirement life in Akwa Ibom State.

The pension schemes for the civil servants in Akwa Ibom State appeared not to have provided adequate plans to positively induce workers' to retirement. So far, the pension policies seem unable to ensure the betterment of retired civil servants particularly as it has to do with social and medical care. This is because poor health and need for health care are major problems of retirees. This defect in pension policies may be responsible for employee's negative perception of old age and retirement. It may further be an indication that the pension schemes in Akwa Ibom State are largely weak and inefficient in terms of motivating workers to retire. Although these may not only be observed in Akwa Ibom State but also the entire Nigerian civil service. The nature and content of pension policies may be responsible for workers' low morale towards retirement (Okechukwu & Ugwu, 2011).

In view of the continuing predicament of retirees, the Reform became necessary to address the problems of the old pension system. It set up the Contributory Pension Scheme (CPS), a replacement of defined benefit scheme with a fully funded, compulsory defined contribution system. It was also followed by the establishment of the Pension Commission (PenCom), to monitor pension related issues (Okechukwu & Ugwu, 2011). One important aspect of the scheme is the ease of access to pension benefits in addition to encouraging workers to save for investment. The scheme is made compulsory for all workers who have more than 3 years to retirement. It introduced contributions to be deducted from the salaries of workers. For additional comfort at old age, it introduced the concept of a worker making additional voluntary contribution and receivable benefits at retirement. Workers are expected to be involved in pension management. The scheme is contributory and fully funded, personalized and very portable. The Scheme has provision for social

security planning and cash payment to replace income lost as a result of retirement or death.

It is for this reason that this study is carried out to determine if motivation to retire among civil servants has to do with Contributory Pension Scheme. The specific contributory pension scheme variables to be considered include: Pension administrators commitment to pension obligation, employee involvement in pension management, encouragement of employee fund investment, receivable benefits at retirement and ease of access to pension benefits and funds.

In Akwa Ibom State, large number of pensioners waiting to collect their entitlement is a common phenomenon. The inability of pensioners to cater for their families and dependents; meet their health needs and other necessities of life has negatively affected motivation towards retirement. Moreover, retirement income is not predictable and adequate. Civil servants do not receive retirement benefits in time. In addition, fund administrators failure to assist civil servants to save for their livelihood after retirement ignites fear towards retirement. The cumbersome process of pension payment itself subjects pensioners in the state to untold hardship. Civil servants thus associate retirement with work role detachment loss of network of social contact, reduced self-esteem, emotional instability, reduced income, relocation, quick death etc. The Akwa Ibom State civil service may not have properly equipped them with the right orientation to face retirement.

In order to address the issue of motivation to retire, civil servants are exposed to periodic counseling with the aim of conditioning them for better retirement life. Importantly, pension policies have been formulated and implemented such as Defined Benefit Scheme, National Provident Fund Scheme, National Social Insurance Trust Fund (NSITF) and Local Government Staff Pension Board. The Nigerian Constitution in sections 180 and 216 states in sub-section 3 and 4 that “pension shall be reviewed every five years or together with any Federal Civil Service salary reviews and pension is non-taxable” (Njunguna, 2010).

However, rather than the earlier existed pension scheme in Akwa Ibom State gingering civil servants to a satisfactory retirement life, they are still being confronted with fear and anxiety. Retirement benefits or entitlements were not be perceived by many prospective retirees as what could enable them to adequately meet their health, nutritional, housing etc. needs in order to age successfully after retirement. The civil servants were not motivated to retire probably because the pension administrators were not committed to pension obligation. Moreover, civil servants themselves were not involved in pension management plans and lacked easy access to pension benefits. Besides, pre-knowledge of entitlement did not boost morale and raised hope for a better future because of its unpredictable nature.

Therefore, in view of the social insecurity, social deprivation, economic and psychological conditions of retirees in Nigeria and specifically in Akwa Ibom State

the challenges associated with the administration of pension and gratuity, the contributory pension scheme was established in 2004. This scheme ensures that the retiree receives pension promptly after retirement without any delay and pension contributions are non-taxable. It assists retirees save towards retirement by ensuring that worker makes monthly contribution from total salary is saved and after retirement he collects 50 percent of total income as gratuity. Therefore, the questions that necessarily come to mind here are: how has the Contributory Pension Scheme affected the motivation to retire? To what extent is employee's motivation to retire affected by Pension Administrators' commitment to pension obligations and workers' involvement in pension management? How is workers' motivation to retire affected by employee fund investment and ease of access to pension benefits? How is motivation to retire affected by receivable/potential benefits at retirement?

The objectives of this study are therefore stipulated as follows:

1. To find out if receivable benefits at retirement do not significantly affect motivation to retire among civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.
2. To discover if ease of access to pension benefits does not significantly affect motivation to retire among civil servants in Akwa Ibom State.

The study was restricted to workers in Akwa Ibom State civil service. The workers in the core ministries shall be used to elicit information for this study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Review of Concepts

The scheme according to Akintunde (2012), Okechukwu (2011) and Ahmad (2010) is contributory in nature. Public sector workers contribute at least 7.5 per cent of their total monthly payment but the military contribute 2.5 per cent. The public sector employer contributes 7.5 per cent on behalf of its workers and 12.5 per cent in the case of the military. Employers and workers in the private sector contribute atleast of 7.5 per cent each. An employer is obliged to deduct and remit contributions to a custodian within days from the day the employee is paid his salary while the custodian shall notify the Pension Fund Administrator within 24 hours of the receipt of such contribution. The retirement benefits are tax exempted.

Voluntary contribution is permitted by the Act. A chance is given to informal sector workers having less than 5 workers to set up Savings Account with a Fund Administrator. In this case, tax relief is only applicable if the amount contributed or part thereof is not take back before five years after the first voluntary contribution was made.

The employee sets up personal account which is permanent even if Fund Administrator is changed. He is allowed to take back 25 percent of the money if less than 50 years at retirement. Also, it is possible to take back a lump sum of 50 per cent if he/she is 50 years or above at the time of retirement and the amount remaining after the lump sum taken back shall be enough to fund programmed taken back or annuity (Ozor, 2006).

Udofot (2012) states key principles of Act 2004 as sustainability, safety and security benefits, transparency, accountability, equity, flexibility, inclusivity, uniformity and practicability. It is for this reason that the pension Reform Act 2004 put planning, administration and regulation under the National Pension Commission, Pension Fund Administrators and pension fund custodian for proper and effective management of the pension fund categories.

i. National Pension Commission

According to Udofot (2012) the “pension reform Act 2004, set up the National Pension Commission (PenCom) as the body to standardize, supervise and guarantee the effective administration of pension matters in Nigeria”. Its duties are to regulate and supervise the scheme, approve, license, regulate and supervise fund administrators. Others include establishing guidelines for funds administration, public enlightenment, and capacity building of fund administrators.

To perform above functions, Nkpoyen (2012) states that the following powers shall be exercised by the commission:

Direct and superintend over pension affairs, agree on conditions of service, obtain information from organizations on retirement benefits, set up offices for use by the Commission. As Director-General is in charge of the Commission, he possesses professional skills. The National Pension Commission has a Chairman and four Commissioners.

The new contributory pension requires pension funds to be managed privately by Pension Fund Administrators and Pension Fund Custodians. Pension Fund Administrators have been duly licensed to set up retirement savings accounts for workers, invest and manage the pension funds in fixed income securities, listed and other instruments as the commission may from time to time prescribe, maintain books of accounts on dealings relating to the pension funds managed by it, and customer service support to RSA holders.

Fund administrators are to custody the assets. The employer sends the contributions directly to the custodian who notifies the Pension Fund Administrator of the receipt of the contribution and the Pension Fund Administrator subsequently credits the retirement savings account of the worker. The custodian will execute transactions and undertake activities relating to the administrations of pension fund investments upon instructions by the pension fund administrator (National Pension Commission, 2008). To stop fraudulent practices companies requesting licence as pension administrators are expected to pay share capital of N150,000.00 and demonstrate capability to perform expected responsibilities. The main difference between the fund administrator and pension fund custodian is that the PFA manages the pension funds and decides which kind of investment to make whereas the PFC hold the pension as well as the assets and acts as directed by Fund Administrators (National Pension Commission, 2008).

ii. Old Pension Scheme and the new Pension Scheme: Benefits and Challenges

In the old scheme no contributions were made and projections were required to be made of the pension's benefits of workers by the employer, with such projections being determined by the workers years of service and earnings. In the old scheme pension responsibilities were entirely the debt burden of the employer and carry with it the probability of inadequate funds to meet workers need (Amujiri, 2009).

According to Nkpoyen (2012), several factors were responsible for the failure of the PAYG system; The PAYG system was inefficient because of to institutional weaknesses and official corruption. Oshiomole (2009) cited in Nkpoyen (2012), ascribed the inefficiency to poor compliance resulting in evasions thus stifling the goals. The layoffs of workers increased the challenges of public sector pension. In 2004, rail way pensioners were owed twenty months of pension money that amounted to about 37 million dollars - the Nigerian Railway Corporation had 18,974 pensioners on its records; due to mass retirement in 1996, about 24 million dollars was required to pay the pensioners every year (Nkpoyen, 2012).

Another very crucial issue for the failure of pre-2004 pension, according to Nkpoyen (2012) was fiscal indiscipline. Over N125 billion funds belonging to the army were reported to have been put in fixed deposited account with several commercial banks within the same period. Under the CPS, the employer is responsible only for making specific contributions on behalf of workers. However, the employer does not guarantee any certain amount upon retirement as he is no longer indebted to the workers upon retirement. Payment to workers on retirement now depends on age, gender, RSA value and final salary (Amujiri, 2009). The new scheme allows for the maintenance of a RSA by each worker, which gives the workers responsibility over the retirement savings, pensioners' fate at retirement are no more determined by employers. It is also argued that personal accounts would provide all workers a higher rate of returns than can be paid under the DB plan.

The new scheme also gives workers an opportunity to pass wealth to survivors in the effect of death. In addition RSA maintained by millions of workers generates a large pool of long – term funds which are available for investment. Owing to economics of scale, the cost of investing such funds tends to be comparably lower than if an individual employee were to undertake the investment on his or her own account. Having a pension scheme that pays workers' benefits in form of annuity programmed take backal affords workers protection against longevity risk, by pooling mortality risk across others.

Employers and workers enjoy labour market flexibility. The worker is free to move with his account as he/she moves to another employment and resident. To the extent, the CPS helps labour mobility, it is an important tool enabling workers and employers to adapt to changing situations, especially in a global environment where change is a constant aspect of social and economic life. Government is expected to benefit in a

number of ways from the new CPS. The scheme according to Akintunde (2012) has provided increased pension responsibility and direction for dealing with liability.

It has also imposed fiscal discipline in the budgetary process because pension obligations are more accurately determined. Apart from the new schemes potential to promote natural savings and economic growth, it has the capability to boost general economic reforms. The schemes also have the capability to support the overall macroeconomic policies of reform through privatization. It also has the potency for furtherance of financial markets.

Receivable Benefits at Retirement and Motivation to Retire

The financial incentive in pension is widely discussed in literature (Nyokabi, 2008). The assumption derives from the literature on “implicit contracts”. Workers are paid less than their productive value at younger years and more than their productive value at older ages. Creating an incentive for workers not to change jobs, and to work harder in anticipation of the future reward”. Pension, “serves as a means of inducing retirement (or at least reducing the effective compensation) among those older workers who would otherwise be paid more than their productive value” (Izrael, 1981).

Igalens and Rouselle (1999) argued that “average number of years spent in retirement has increased steadily, partly as a result of increasing life expectancy, and partly because of younger retirement ages. Between 1950 and 2000, labour force participation rates of older men dropped significantly from 46 percent to 18 percent among men age sixty five and older, and from 87 percent to 68 percent among men between ages fifty five and sixty four. Among women, the large increase in labour force participation at younger age is absent at older ages, suggesting the offsetting decision to retire earlier among women as well”. Monetary benefits provided by pension influence retirement behaviour according to the study.

In a study carried out by Woodbury (2001) among twenty large US Corporations, incentives and motivation for business retirement policies including the desire for older workers to retire were identified. In some cases retirement incentives are intentional or secondary to the policies central motivation.

Woodbury asserted that the “practical application of paternalistic values in the design of pension plan is most clearly represented in the widespread use of explicit income replacement targets for retired workers”. Income replacement target seeks to target according to him is to “identify the percentage of pre-retirement income that the company believes will provide an appropriate standard of living in retirement”. Concerns about retirement standard of living, retiree welfare, and income replacement suggest a very different view of retirement benefits which encouraged workers to go into retirement without fear.

Ease of Access to Pension Benefits and Motivation to Retire

Ease of access to pension benefits is a fundamental objective of contributory pension scheme. This commitment is expressed in the scheme's strong desire to care for retirees (Owojori 2008). Orifowomo (2006) stated that, "for the workers preparing to retire from service, the knowledge of delay in pension benefit could lead to embarrassing circumstances typified in inability to pay rent, inability to pay children school fees, poor dietary intake that might result in malnourishments, inaccessibility to adequate and proper Medicare, inability to meet with maturing social and financial obligations". These may result in negative attitude towards retirement.

Ahmad (2008) stressed that ease of access to pension benefits is positively linked with motivation to retire. This implies that the workers on retirement are entitled to health care and to be sincerely managed. Ahmad (2008) stated that where accessibility to pension is not assured, on retirement, workers may prefer to work than to retire leading to low motivation towards retirement. They are positively motivated towards retirement when pension benefits are regularly paid and enough to take care of their welfare needs during retirement.

Access to pension benefits relates to motivation to retire in that such workers will embrace better welfare benefits guarantee their financial stability by providing income for retirement (World at Work, 2007). Dostal & Cessey (2007) state that the contributory pension scheme has inbuilt employee welfare plan and benefits which serve to motivate workers towards positive retirement outlook. Dostal and Cessey (2007) observed that because workers have access to pension funds with ease, it is possible for workers to experience an enhanced wellbeing. They have easy access to pay and they forms an important part of total reward package.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework is discussed under the following sub-headings:

The Deferred Wage Income Theory

The proponents of this theory are Malaski and Capele (1982) and March (1980). According to the theory, the pension plan is a device for deferring certain benefits till the time of retirements, basic premise of the theory is that the employer provides pension payment in place of current services. The deferred funds usually lead to individuals savings. The employer derives immense advantage in providing a pension plan. Thus, firms offer pension because of economies of scale (Freeman, 1981).

The theory argues that it is possible for the employer to receive cash flow benefits in such a way that the present level of deferred wages exceeds what is required for funding. The theory incorporates a long term and inherent labour contract between the employer and the employee with several imports for the mutual relationship. The mutuality of benefits between the employer and employee makes the theory very unique.

Based on the theory, the contributory pension scheme is highly beneficial to both the civil servants and the government shared responsibility over the retirement plans and savings. The civil servant has an opportunity through the pension funds administration to maintain a large stock of funds for long term investment later in life. Again, because of economics of scale, it becomes cheaper investing such funds than if individual and servants were to do it on his own. It also implies that deferred payment translates to the payment of civil servants' entitlements in form of installment take backs. This gives protection to the workers against prolonged life span by sharing the mortality risk with others.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The research design adopted for this study was survey research design. The surveys are used when it is desirable to find the distribution and interrelationship of certain characteristics among large numbers of people. For this work, this research design was considered most appropriate because of the nature of the study. It was quantitative in nature and relied on only the use of questionnaire for data collection.

3.2 Research Area

This research was conducted in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The state is located in the south eastern part (south south) of Nigeria lying between latitude 4° 32'N and 5° 30'N and longitude 8° 30' East of Greenwich meridian.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised all the workers of the civil service (ministries, departments and agencies) in Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria. The total number of ministries, departments and agencies is fifty – five (55) with a total population of thirteen thousand and seventy seven (13,077) civil servants male (6,757) and female (6,320) (Akwa Ibom State Man Power Statistics, 2012).

3.4 Sampling Procedure

Two sampling procedure was adopted; firstly, purposive sampling technique was used to select only ministries excluding departments and agencies. This is because the state ministries have the bulk of civil servants and the different categories of workers. Secondly, simple random sampling procedure was used to select civil servants from the twenty state ministries. Since the researcher's specific concern is with the state civil servants working in the ministries. The researcher purposively studied 60 per cent of the civil servants in the senior staff category since this category is closer to retirement, this amounted to seven hundred and seventy eight (778) senior civil servants and 40 per cent of the civil servant in the junior staff category, this amounted to five hundred and ten (510) junior staff.

To draw the actual respondents for the study, the researcher adopted proportionate to size sampling technique in each ministry. This amounted to seven hundred and seventy eight (778) senior civil servants and five hundred and ten junior civil servants (510) from the study area amounting to one thousand two hundred and thirty (1288).

In this section the main variables of the study are identified, their mean and standard deviation calculated. The Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 18 was used to perform frequency count, percentages, mean and standard deviation.

4. FINDINGS

4.1 Data Presentation

The main variables of the study are identified, their mean and standard deviation calculated. The Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 18 was used to perform frequency count, percentages, mean and standard deviation.

Table 4.1 presents the mean and standard deviation of the independent and dependent variables in the study. It reveals that the mean score of civil servants in involvement in pension management was 16.82, with a standard deviation of 3.01; mean for encouragement of employee and investment was 18.72 with a standard deviation of 2.44; mean of ease of access to pension benefits was 18.19, a standard deviation of 3.23; the mean for receivable benefits at retirement was 18.19 with a standard deviation of 3.99; mean for motivation to retire was 15.73 with standard deviation of 2.55. This implied that respondents agreed above average to the various items measuring contributory pension scheme.

Table 4.1: Demographic information of respondents

	Variable	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Gender	Male	542	44.1
	Female	688	55.9
	Total	1230	100
Age	14-19 years	7	0.6
	20-25 years	167	13.6
	26-31 years	261	21.2
	32 years and above	795	64.6
	Total	1230	100
Marital status	Single	371	30.1
	Married	859	69.8
	Total	1230	100
Educational qualification	FSLC	44	3.6
	WAEC/NECO	252	20.5
	OND/B.Sc	847	68.9
	M.Sc/M.Ed/Ph.D	87	7.1
	Total	1230	100
Years in service	0-9 years	436	35.4
	10-18 years	206	16.7
	19 years and above	588	47.8
	Total	1230	100

Rank/position	Senior staff	778	63.25
	Junior staff	452	36.75
	Total	1230	100
Length in present position	1-3 years	491	39.9
	4-6 years	447	36.3
	7 years and above	292	23.7
	Total	1230	100

Source: Field work, 2014

The result in Table 4.1 reveals respondents' demographic information. The respondents' responses to the questionnaire reveal that 688 respondents representing 55.9 percent are females while 542 representing 44.1 percent are males. These descriptions seem to be a true representation of the population.

Table 4.2: Potential benefits after retirement and motivation to retire

S/N	Statement	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%
1.	Workers on retirement can enjoy atleastlevel of essential protection to act as a safety net in the event of death.	185	(15.0)	720	(58.5)	225	(18.3)	100	(8.1)
2.	Motivation to retire is lacking because retirement benefits do not take care of serious illnesses or disabilities.	271	(22.0)	209	(17.0)	631	(51.3)	119	(9.7)
3.	Motivation to retire is lacking because workers will be willing to retire if retirement benefits and savings give retirees flexibility to meet the needs of their families.	388	(31.5)	263	(21.4)	476	(38.7)	104	(8.4)
4.	Retirement benefits do not provide workers choice to meet their social needs and so many workers are afraid to retire.	263	(21.4)	461	(37.5)	355	(28.9)	151	(12.3)
5.	Motivation to retire decrease because retirement robs the employee of opportunity to access better health care.	256	(20.8)	207	(16.8)	451	(36.7)	316	(25.7)
6.	Workers do not receive enough retirement benefits and this affects workers physical and mental well-being on retirement.	429	(34.9)	175	(14.2)	341	(27.7)	285	(23.2)
7.	Workers' accumulated contributions plus earnings at retirement are enough benefits to motivate them to retire.	283	(23.0)	216	(17.6)	517	(42.0)	214	(17.4)

Source: Fieldwork, 2014

Table 4.2 indicates responses on potential benefits after retirement and motivation to retire. The responses in this table will be collapsed into agreed and disagreed. Majority of respondents, 73.5 per cent (n = 905) agreed that as workers on retirement they can enjoy atleast level of essential protection to act as a safety net in the event of death. Nevertheless, 26.4 per cent (n = 335) respondents disagreed that workers on retirement may not enjoy at least level of essential protection.

Table 4.3: Ease of access to pension benefits and motivation to retire

S/N	Statement	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%
1.	I am motivated to retire because my income level will not reduce after retirement because I will have access to my pension funds.	228	(18.5)	471	(38.3)	364	(29.6)	167	(13.6)
2.	If I had a choice, I would prefer not to retire because of delay in payment of pension.	215	(17.5)	230	(18.7)	690	(56.1)	95	(7.7)
3.	Motivation to retire increases access to pension benefit t takes away the embarrassment of inability to pay children school fees and poor dietary intake on retirement.	237	(9.8)	606	(21.1)	260	(49.3)	127	(19.9)
4.	My negative attitude towards retirement is because the meager pension benefit will disable me cater for my needs.	190	(15.4)	222	(18.0)	456	(37.1)	362	(29.4)
5.	With ease of access to pension benefits, workers are willing to retire because they can still live their normal life style after retirement.	442	(35.9)	471	(38.3)	161	(13.1)	156	(12.7)
6.	Workers on retirement do not enjoy health and safety despite ease of access to pension benefits.	167	(13.6)	206	(16.7)	295	(24.0)	562	(45.7)
7.	Motivation to retire will increase workers access to welfare benefits to maintain their standard of living after retirement.	501	(40.7)	358	(29.1)	257	(20.9)	114	(9.3)

Source: Fieldwork, 2014

TABLE 4.3 indicates responses on ease of access to pension benefits and motivation to retire. The responses in this table will be collapsed into agreed and disagreed. It is seen from the table that 56.8 per cent (n = 699) respondents agreed that they are motivated to retire because their income level will not reduce after retirement since they will have access to their pension funds. This was objected to by 43.3 per cent (n = 531) of respondents. This meant that they feel less motivated to retire because their

income level will reduce. Again, 36.3 percent ($n = 445$) respondents agreed that if they had a choice they would prefer not to retire because of delay in payment of pension while 63.8 per cent ($n = 785$) respondents disagreed meaning that they would still retire not because of delay in pension payment.

4.2 Discussion of findings

Table 4.2 indicates responses on potential benefits after retirement and motivation to retire. The responses in this table will be collapsed into agreed and disagreed. Majority of respondents, 73.5 per cent ($n = 905$) agreed that as workers on retirement they can enjoy at least level of essential protection to act as a safety net in the event of death. Nevertheless, 26.4 per cent ($n = 335$) respondents disagreed that workers on retirement may not enjoy at least level of essential protection.

The table shows that 39 per cent ($n = 480$) respondents confessed that motivation to retire is lacking because retirement benefits do not take care of serious illness or disability. On this same issue, majority of respondents, 61 per cent ($n = 750$) disagreed implying that motivation to retire is lacking because retirement benefits do not take care of serious illness or disability. These categories of workers believe that with retirement benefits, health care needs could be addressed. It is also observed that 52.9 per cent ($n = 651$) respondents confessed that workers will be willing to retire if retirement benefits and savings give retirees flexibility to meet the needs of their families. However, 47.1 per cent ($n = 580$) disagreed.

The findings of Coile, Courtney, Diamond, Gruber & Joistin (2002) are consistent with this study. They assert that before the full retirement age or service year of thirty-five years, the employee needs to be well informed of his or her entitlements after retirement. This according to them will encourage them for intelligent use of the entitlement due to them. This present study confirms that knowing the entitlement quite in time encourages the retirees. This helps to raise their hope for a good tomorrow and long life.

These findings are in harmony with the Commission on Fiscal Responsibility and Reform (2010) which says that Social Security Administration should provide information to the public to encourage better retirement planning. This is supported by Munnell & Sass (2008) who opines that extended workforce involvement may be the solution to the retirement income situation which workers often encounter. The findings of the study also agree with Spiegelman (2009) that retirees should not only be acquainted with their potential benefits or entitlements but should be allowed to enjoy it at the appropriate time.

Ease of Access to Pension Benefits and Motivation to Retire The result of analysis of hypothesis four revealed that a significant relationship exists between ease of access to pension benefits and motivation to retire. This was confirmed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis. It was revealed by 70 per cent ($n = 901$) respondents that motivation to retire is positive because access to pension benefits

takes away the embarrassment of inability to pay children school fees and even poor dietary intake. The Pearson Correlation analysis indicated a significant relationship $r(1229) = 0.081$.

These findings agree with Ahmad (2008) that ease of access to pension benefits is positively linked with motivation to retire. Workers on retirement have the privilege of enjoying healthier life style as well as the right to manage fairly just like someone in employment.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The faulty assessment of pension liabilities, impulsive increases in pension without comparable funding arrangement, etc. were all part of the old pension scheme. These negatively affected motivation to retire by civil servants. The contributory pension scheme, as shown in this study, has been able to address these shortcomings.

The scheme allows the funds' administrators to become more committed, encourages employee fund investment, ensures ease of access to pension benefits and sensitizes civil servants on receivable/potential benefits prior to retirement. This makes the scheme an attractive device for smooth retirement of civil servant. The contributory pension scheme, as assessed in this study, is seen by many prospective retirees in Akwa Ibom State as what enables them meet health, nutritional, learning, physical exercise, housing and social needs in order to age successfully after retirement in the civil service.

5.2 Recommendation

Since ease of access to pension benefits is positively linked with motivation to retire, pension fund administrators should put in place appropriate measures to ensure that retired civil servants have access to their funds.

Fund administrators should maintain their high level of commitment to management of the pension scheme since no reasonable employee will hesitate to retire when they are due.

REFERENCES

- Akintunde, I. (2012) Pension policy and issues of retirement in Nigeria. Ibadan: Pat-Mag Press.
- Ahmad, M. K. (2008b). Corporate Governance in the Pension Industry: A paper presented at the Adebayo.
- Amujiri, B. A. (2009). The new contributory pension scheme in Nigeria: a critical assessment NJPALG, XIV, I, 137-152

- Bassey, A. (2011) Impact of pension scheme on workers post-retirement life. *Journal of business and Management Review*, 23(6), 47-53.
- Bisong, K. R. (2011). Employee pensions and work performance in public service. *Public Administration Review*, 66(8), 213-221.
- Coile, Courtney, Diamond, P., Gruber, J. and Alain, J. (2002). Delays in Claiming Social Security Benefits. *Journal of Public Economic*, 84(3), 357-385.
- Dostal, J. M. and Cessey, B. H. (2007). Pension Reforms in Nigeria; How to learn others; 57th Political Studies Association, Annual Conference 11 to 13 April, 2007, Bath.
- IBTC Pension Managers (2008). Planning for your retirement.
- Igalens, J. and Rousell, P. (1999). A study of relationship between compensation package, work motivation and job satisfaction. *J. Organ. Behaviour*, 20(14), 1003-1025.
- Jonathan, G. (2009). Nigeria: The fear of retirement, Daily trust. Retrieved from <http://allafrica.com/stories/200910050546htmm>
- Lazear, E. (1981). Agency, earning profiles, productivity and hours restrictions. *American Economic Review*, 71(4), 606–620.
- Munnell, A. H. and Sass, A. S. (2008). Working Longer: The Solution to the Retirement Income Challenge. Washington, DC: Brookings Institution Press
- Njunguna, S. (2010). Personal pension scheme, an attractive saving option. *HR Management Journal*, 6.
- Nkпойen, F. (2012). Social welfare as social development: a socio-historic Foundation. Calabar: University of Calabar press.
- Nyokabi, C. (2008). Retirement benefits authority. Retrieved on Feb. 22, 2014 from <http://www.oppapers.com/essays/Retrievement, 5.15pm>
- Okechukwu, E. and Ugwu, S. (2011). The laws and administration of retirement in Nigeria: A historical approach. *Kuwait chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Reviews*, 1(2), 1-11.
- Orifowomo, O. A. (2006). A Critical Appraisal of Pension System Reforms in Nigeria. 10 Gonz. J. Int'l L. <http://www.gonzajil.org/>

- Ozor, E. (2006). Review of factors that slow down the processing of retirement benefits. A paper presented at the workshop organized by the Institute of Chartered secretaries and Administration of Nigeria, held at Modotel Enegu, between 14th-16th May.
- Udofot, P. U. (2012). Rationale for pension reform in Nigeria; *Business Day* May 05
- NASB (2010): Statement of Accounting Standard 8: Accounting for Retirement Benefit
- Spiegelman, R. (2009). Social security: making the Most of Your Benefits. Research & Strategies: Retirement Planning Article. San Francisco, CA: Charles Schwab.
- Worldatwork (2007). Handbook of Compensation, benefits and total rewards. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons.